

Semi-Autonomous Interaction Framework for Contact-based Operations with Commercial UAVs in GNSS-denied Environments

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Abstract—Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are being increasingly established for autonomous contact-based inspection of industrial assets, reducing the risk of errors by human operators. However, challenges remain in the navigation under unreliable Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) signals, or in the detection and interaction with the inspection surface, which limits the autonomy level of current UAV industrial technologies. This paper presents a semi-autonomous framework which combines automated target detection and interaction in GNSS-denied environments, with supervision commands by a human operator, to increase both safety and reliability. Our framework is composed of: (i) a camera-based onboard odometry solution for positioning the UAV in GNSS-denied conditions, (ii) a target-detection and filtering algorithm which estimates the orientation and position of the interaction target and (iii) a visual servoing strategy for approaching and contacting the target. The proposed framework is developed completely in ROS, and can be used with any commercial UAV. The framework is validated through outdoor flights, where a UAV detects and contacts a target on a vertical pipe.

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial inspection at height presents hazardous working environments for human operators, subsequently resulting in high cost and low time efficiency [1]. Recently, UAVs equipped with manipulators have emerged as an alternative to human inspection workers due to their effectiveness in reducing the duration, costs, and risks associated with tasks in challenging and hard-to-reach areas [2]. While they have demonstrated their potential in inspecting civil infrastructure [3], [4], power lines [5], [6], pipelines [7] and refineries [8], current UAV contact-based inspection still requires intense human assistance [9]. A human operator acting as a high-level supervisor for the UAV is often required by law and improves mission's safety. Additionally,

This work has been supported by the MARTIN project, grant PID2022-143267OB-I00, funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU, and by the AEROTRAIN Marie Skłodowska-Curie (MSCA-ITN-2020-953454) and SIMAR (HE-CL4-2021-101070604) projects, funded by the European Commission.

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Fig. 1: Autonomous target detection and interaction with a vertical pipe using a UAV with a static manipulator attached.

higher automation level were proven to reduce the workload and increase the performance of human operators in [10]. For this reason, the human pilot plays an important role in the control architecture, coordinating the autonomous pipeline. On the other hand, to increase the autonomy of current UAV technologies, challenges remain about navigation in GNSS-denied environments, or in the detection and interaction with inspection points.

Concerning GNSS-denied navigation, significant advancements were made in LiDAR-based Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) for UAVs [11]. However, while 3D LiDARs can offer accurate and reliable self-localization among different environments, their cost can be prohibitive depending on the application. Moreover, their mechanics are delicate and have considerable weight, further reducing their applicability in UAV navigation. For these reasons, camera-based techniques provide a good alternative for UAV navigation in terms of cost, accuracy and reliability [10], [12].

Furthermore, visual-based solutions are also effectively applied in object detection for physical interactions with UAVs [13], [14]. Some solutions rely on advanced neural network approaches [15] while others on more traditional computer vision solutions [16], where many times a depth camera is employed as the sensor of choice. Such solutions were proven especially suited for infrastructure and bridge inspection [17], [18], where the UAV can fly in the proximity of the building, track the points of interest, and interact with them [19].

However, most of the works in the literature show either indoor experiments, or outdoor inspection tasks in areas with GPS available. While they demonstrate various target detection and visual servoing techniques, to the best of our knowledge there is no full semi-autonomous inspection task, automated mission combined with human supervision commands, conducted fully in a GNSS-denied environment. This poses indeed additional difficulties because of possibly drifting odometry, especially in the target estimation and during the inspection approaching phase, which require careful consideration. Also, this further strengthens the need of a human pilot in the loop, coordinating the autonomous pipeline and increasing the overall mission’s safety.

A. Contributions

We present a semi-autonomous framework which combines automated target detection and interaction in GNSS-denied environments, with supervision commands by a human operator. These supervision commands allow for switching between different flight modes at the operator’s discretion, ensuring safe interaction. In particular, we first propose a lightweight target detector and estimator to obtain the target’s pose. Then we design a modular control architecture able to autonomously track and contact the target, under the supervision commands of a human operator. We focus on a pipe inspection use case, where the target detection module has been designed to detect the target shown in Figure 1. Finally, we validate our system through outdoor pipe interaction experiments. In particular:

- We design a modular detection and servoing framework tailored for GNSS-denied navigation.
- We actively integrate the human pilot in the loop to increase the robustness and safety of the architecture.
- We validate our semi-autonomous architecture with several outdoor inspection tasks.

While there are already several aerial platforms designed for contact-based operations, they typically rely on advanced designs and are developed with custom autopilots [7], [8], [20], [21], hindering the widespread integration of standard multirotors for contact-based inspections. Compared to other solutions, our approach utilizes a commercial multirotor with coplanar propellers, which are the most common. In addition, the manipulator installed is a 0DoF (Degree of Freedom) static manipulator, eliminating the control challenges associated with the coupling dynamic. Furthermore, our framework is entirely developed in ROS, easing its integration into other commercial aerial platforms.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II gives an overview of the proposed framework. Section III presents hardware setup of the aerial manipulator. Section IV describes the self-localization algorithm for GNSS-denied environments, while Section V outlines the autonomous target detection algorithm. Then, the visual servoing controller and the target interaction are explained in Section VI. The experimental validation of the proposed framework is presented in Section VII. Finally, the conclusions of this work are summarized in Section VIII.

Fig. 2: Components of the proposed framework. The onboard Intel D455 camera provides video feed for the Target Estimator, which provides the position and orientation of the target to the onboard controllers. The pilot can manually control the velocity of the UAV, or switch into servoing or interaction mode, in which the UAV autonomously tracks and contacts the target. The low-level velocity and attitude controller are provided by the onboard Pixhawk. This also provides the EKF2 state estimator, which fuses the IMU and T265 odometry estimate to fly in GNSS-denied environments.

II. FRAMEWORK OVERVIEW

The proposed target detection and interaction framework is composed of three main elements:

- An onboard odometry solution, which allows the system to fly in GNSS-denied environments.
- A target detector and estimator, which gets the video stream from an onboard RGBD camera and produces the pose coordinates of the target.
- An autonomous servoing and interaction controller, which allows the UAV to track and contact the target.

The control pipeline is managed by a human pilot, which manually flies the UAV in the proximity of the pipe, obtains visual feedback from the target estimator and enables the autonomous servoing and interaction controller once the target is locked. The pilot’s presence further increases the interaction’s safety as falling back to manual control of the UAV is always possible. The different components and their interconnections are in Figure 2. While the D455 camera provides the video feed for the target detector, the T265 odometry estimate is fed into the PX4 [22] EKF (Extended Kalman Filter) state estimator and fused with the IMU to obtain the UAV’s odometry.

III. PLATFORM HARDWARE SETUP

The UAV used in this work is based on the hexarotor Tarot 680 frame, with the KDE2814XF-775 motors and KDE Direct UAS 35+ ESCs with 13×5 inch propellers. A Pixhawk Cube Orange autopilot controls the attitude and position of the platform and is connected to a LattePanda 3 Delta, which acts as companion computer. In addition, the UAV is equipped with two cameras: an Intel RealSense D455 camera and an Intel RealSense T265 camera. The T265 camera provides the platform’s odometry estimate, while the D455 camera, looking forward in the manipulation direction,

Fig. 3: Hardware setup of a UAV equipped with a static manipulator to contact the target, a T265 camera for odometry estimates and a D455 camera to detect the interaction target.

Fig. 4: The illustration of the contact scenarios using the aerial vehicle equipped with the proposed end-effector. r_c : the radius of the arc on the end-effector around the body frame origin O_B . α : the maximum allowed tilting angle of the vehicle body.

is used for detecting the target. The system is powered by a 10000 mAh-4s LiPo battery, mounted on the lower part of the platform. All the components are shown in Figure 3.

The D455 camera is mounted 20 cm below the platform with an upward angle of 30 degrees. This assembly guarantees that the target is not entirely covered by the manipulator while approaching the target.

A. A Novel End-Effector Design

To enable physical interaction using a commercially available 4-DoFs aerial vehicle, various manipulators can be attached based on the task requirements. For pushing tasks used in contact-based inspections, rigid links are often employed. However, these do not guarantee contact point accuracy due to the inherent coupling of linear and angular dynamics in aerial vehicles. The vehicle must tilt to exert a stable pushing force, making precise control over the contact point challenging when using only a rigid link. Alternatively,

high-DoFs robotic arms can improve accuracy, but they add weight and complexity to the system due to additional actuators and control requirements.

To address these limitations, we propose a novel, lightweight end-effector design (see Figure 3 and Figure 4) that allows for accurate interaction with vertical surfaces using a rigidly attached link. The end-effector is designed to reduce system complexity while maintaining precision. We define the body frame as $\mathcal{F}_B = \{O_B; X_B, Y_B, Z_B\}$, where the origin O_B is located at the aerial vehicle's center of gravity (CoG). A rigid link is aligned with the body's positive X_B axis. The end-effector takes the shape of an arc with radius r_c around the CoG, as shown in see Figure 4. We define α as the maximum tilt angle of the vehicle during pushing. The arc length of the end-effector is determined by this angle α . For our system, α is set to 10° , which allows for generating a pushing force of up to 0.5 kg. This design ensures that the distance between the contact point and the CoG remains constant at $r_c = 0.5$ m when the vehicle tilts within the range $[0, \alpha]$.

Furthermore, the pushing force remains aligned with the CoG, minimizing torque around it. This setup reduces the impact of contact wrenches on the vehicle during interaction, enhancing system stability during tasks.

IV. LOCALIZATION IN GNSS-DENIED ENVIRONMENTS

Throughout the design process, extensive experiments were conducted with GNSS-based localization, revealing significant errors that were consistently noticeable whenever the platform approached large structures or cluttered surrounding space. Furthermore, the risk of collision with nearby infrastructures deemed the option to localize via GNSS unreliable. To overcome this, the integration of VIO (Visual-Inertial Odometry) from the Intel T265 tracking camera with the Pixhawk flight controller stack was proven to be a pivotal advancement in achieving robust GNSS-denied localization to conduct autonomous flight. More specifically, VIO odometry was fused together with the Pixhawk's IMU data inside the PX4 EKF.

The seamless integration mitigated the challenges posed by the GNSS-denied environment, ensuring sufficient precision during the navigation. Notably, after extensive investigation, we concluded that the most suitable orientation for the T265 camera was to place it looking down to the ground. This decision was crucial to avoid the adverse effects of the sun and various shadows in the camera background feed that, at certain moments, severely degraded the VIO odometry estimates. Also, it was important to isolate the camera from the vibrations of the propellers. The two most effective ways were to either using a dedicated dampening material at the camera attachment, or connecting it to an element of great inertia, like the UAV's battery. These strategic adjustments improved the system's resilience and efficacy during the real-world field robotics experiments.

V. TARGET DETECTION AND ESTIMATION

A. Target Detection

The goals of the target detection approach are twofold: (i) to determine the target's location relative to the UAV, and (ii) to identify the normal of the target surface. Both are necessary to successfully track and contact the object in the following servoing and interaction controllers. In the current scenario, the target is identified as a series of concentric circles. Each circle has black edges, with the four innermost circles colored in a sequence from the center outward: yellow, red, blue, and black. The RealSense D455 camera is employed for target detection as it provides both RGB and depth measurements.

Remark. *Although the proposed target has a specific shape and colors, the modularity of the framework would allow to modify only this module to detect other types of targets, such as cracks and corrosion. Since this work aims to present the complete interaction framework, the detection of real defects like cracks or corrosion is out of the scope and is proposed as future work.*

Given that the target possesses distinct attributes, such as a circular shape and unique colors, we opt for a traditional computer vision approach for its detection. This method stands out in contrast to machine learning-based techniques for its lower computational demands, ease of implementation, and no need of extensive datasets. The process for detecting the target's center and its normal involves the following steps:

1) *Target's center:* The target center is obtained through the RGB image by using a circle detection algorithm in combination with a series of image filters.

The original image first undergoes pre-progress filtering for primary denoising and smoothing. The core detection

Fig. 5: Target detection pipeline. The image preprocessing together with the different color and circle filtering are shown. At the end the image detection result is used with the depth data to obtain the target's normal.

Algorithm 1 Target Estimation

Input:

Target's global position filtered: ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t \in \mathbb{R}^3$,
 Target's raw global position: ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t^R \in \mathbb{R}^3$,
 Target's global position filtered for outliers: ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t^{OD} \in \mathbb{R}^3$,
 Detected outliers: $DL \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Output:

Target's global position filtered: ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t \in \mathbb{R}^3$,

Params:

Averaging window size: $N \in \mathbb{Z}^+$,
 3D euclidean distance threshold: $d_h \in \mathbb{R}^+$,
 Maximum number of outliers detected: $MNDO \in \mathbb{Z}^+$,

```

1: while true do
2:   if firstdetection then
3:      ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t[n] \leftarrow {}_w\mathbf{p}_t^R$ 
4:   else
5:      ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t^{OD}[n] \leftarrow$  Equation (1)
6:     if  ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t^R$  is outlier then
7:        $DL \leftarrow DL + 1$ 
8:     end if
9:     if  $DL > MNDO$  then
10:      Clear the list of  ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t^{OD}$ 
11:       ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t^{OD}[n] \leftarrow {}_w\mathbf{p}_t^R$ 
12:       $DL \leftarrow 0$ 
13:    end if
14:     ${}_w\mathbf{p}_t[n] \leftarrow$  Equation (2)
15:  end if
16: end while
  
```

method applies Canny edge detection [23] to delineate all scene features, coupled with Hough transform for circle detection [24] to identify a list of potential circle candidates.

The post-processing phase involves two primary outlier filters. Color filtering is performed in the HSV space given the target's distinct color features. This process masks the scene, retaining circles that match the target's color. Considering the UAV operates under varying illumination and spectral conditions, and the camera's white balance and color processing may not consistently replicate the exact color of the entire scene, the target could manifest in different hues. Hence, our color filter is configured with a relatively wide range to encompass all possible appearances of the target. This approach has proven effective in excluding most false detection results from the background environment. In the end, concentric circle filtering is executed, with two key functions: a) filtering out non-concentric results and b) consolidating multi-detected concentric circles into a singular circle, retaining the innermost one with a unified center, which is the average of the effective detected centers.

Once the circle center has been identified, we can obtain its depth coordinate from the depth measurements, obtaining the full target coordinates ${}_C\mathbf{p}_t = (x_{cam}, y_{cam}, z_{cam})$ in camera frame C .

2) *Target's normal:* Once the center coordinates are obtained, we collect a grid of 50x50 points around it and treat

Algorithm 2 Visual servoing

Input:

Target's normal axis: ${}_W z_t \in \mathbb{R}^3$,
Target's position: ${}_W p_t \in \mathbb{R}^3$,
UAV's position: ${}_W p_u \in \mathbb{R}^3$,
UAV's manipulator axis: ${}_W x_u \in \mathbb{R}^3$,
Mode switch: $m \in \{Manual, Servoing, Interaction\}$

Output:

UAV's linear speed command: ${}_W v_c \in \mathbb{R}^3$,
UAV's yaw speed command: $\psi_c \in \mathbb{R}$

Params:

Safety distance from target: $l \in \mathbb{R}$,
Linear and yaw velocity gains: $k_v, k_\psi \in \mathbb{R}$,
Constant approaching speed: $v_a \in \mathbb{R}$

```
1: while true do
2:    ${}_W p_r \leftarrow {}_W p_u + l {}_W z_t$ 
3:    $\Delta\psi \leftarrow angularError({}_W z_t, {}_W x_u)$ 
4:   if  $m$  is Manual then
5:      ${}_W v_c, \psi_c \leftarrow getCommandsFromRC()$ 
6:   else if  $m$  is Servoing then
7:      ${}_W v_c \leftarrow k_v ({}_W p_r - {}_W p_u)$ 
8:      $\psi_c \leftarrow k_\psi \Delta\psi$ 
9:   else if  $m$  is Interaction then
10:     ${}_W d_{u,t} \leftarrow ({}_W p_t - {}_W p_u) / \|{}_W p_r - {}_W p_u\|$ 
11:    while  $m$  is Interaction do
12:       ${}_W v_c \leftarrow v_a {}_W d_{u,t}$ 
13:       $\psi_c \leftarrow 0$ 
14:    end while
15:   end if
16: end while
```

them as a plane, computing their normal ${}_C z_t$ using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) [25]. The entire detection pipeline is illustrated in Figure 5.

B. Target estimation

While the target detection algorithm demonstrated notable accuracy, a subsequent filtering was deemed necessary to ensure robust detection. This step aimed to reject false positives and outliers that may arise in cluttered environments. The filtering mechanism was designed to act on the target's center in the world frame, denoted with ${}_W p_t$. Considering the world frame coordinates of the point of interest simplifies the estimation problem, as it's position in the world is constant.

The filtering mechanism comprises two main elements: an outlier detection step, which handles false positives, and an averaging filter. The averaging filter serves to eliminate high-frequency noise, resulting in a smoother and more refined detection process. The outlier detection filter is formulated as follows, let

$${}_W p_t^{OD}[n] = \begin{cases} {}_W p_t^R[n], & e^{3D} < d_{th} \\ {}_W p_t[n-1], & e^{3D} \geq d_{th} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

be the filter's output, where $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ is the discrete time samples. Then, $e^{3D} = e^{3D}({}_W p_t[n-1], {}_W p_t^R[n])$ denotes the

3D Euclidean distance between the unfiltered detected target center ${}_W p_t^R[n] \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and the previously filtered detected target center ${}_W p_t[n-1] \in \mathbb{R}^3$. This ensures that all the raw measurements that don't agree with the current estimate, i.e. that are too far away from it, are filtered by the outlier detection. Furthermore, the averaging low-pass filter can be formulated as:

$${}_W p_t[n] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} {}_W p_t^{OD}[n-k], \quad (2)$$

where $N \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ denotes the filtering window, i.e., how many samples are included in the average. Since when an outlier is detected we feed the filter with the previous estimate (in the absence of newer admissible data), the filter could become overconfident if too many outliers are detected in a row. This is actually a situation that presents itself in case of drifting odometry or initial misdetections, since the previous estimated position of the target is not valid anymore. For this reason, we introduce a parameter denoted as MNDO (Maximum Number of Detected Outliers). Thus, when the number of detected outliers exceeds MNDO, the estimates switches over the new target and the framework continues the inspection accordingly. The complete process is described in Algorithm 1.

VI. VISUAL SERVOING AND TARGET INTERACTION

The controller used to reach and touch the target (see Figure 7) is composed of two main elements: the first visual servoing part is responsible for approaching the target and align the manipulator such to point towards it; the second part is responsible of covering the last distance that separates the UAV and the target in a straight line, until interaction.

The main difference lies in the fact that the visual servoing part actively corrects the UAV pose with respect to new pose estimates of the target, while the final interaction keeps the target's pose estimation constant. This is because the target estimation could degrade when the target is very close to the UAV, wrongly correcting its pose in the last centimeters before the interaction. Since the target is static and the drift of the onboard odometry is negligible in the few seconds required for the interaction, freezing the estimation is indeed possible. Algorithm 2 gives an overview of the visual servoing and target interaction approach. In particular, the pilot is in charge of switching control mode between: *Manual* in which the pilot sends velocity commands to the UAV with the RC, *Servoing* in which the visual servoing algorithm pulls the UAV at a safety distance in front of the target (1.0m in our experiments), and *Interaction* in which the UAV just moves in the direction of the target with a constant linear speed, eventually touching it. After a successful target inspection (or in case of failure), the pilot can take over manually again and safely get away from the target and towards the next.

VII. FIELD EXPERIMENTS

To validate the proposed framework, the UAV flights in an outdoors scenario where a vertical pipe of a 1 m diameter was installed, as Figure 1 shows. We validate

Fig. 6: Different instants of the outdoor validation flights.

Fig. 7: The UAV with its manipulator axis (red) approaching the target (with target's normal in blue). The world frame is in the bottom left. All the relevant quantities for the visual servoing are highlighted.

our framework through a flight where the pilot takes-off in *Manual* mode, switch to *Servoing* mode and finally activates the *Interaction* mode to contact the target. At the end, the pilot activates again the *Manual* mode to get away from the pipe and landing. Figure 6 shows these different phases of the outdoors flight.

A. Target estimation results

The overall performance of autonomous interaction relies heavily on a dependable target estimate, as a significant deviation in the contact angle and position can lead to unsafe conditions for the UAV. Figure 8 illustrates the 3D target detection. Unfiltered (raw) detections are represented in black, while filtered detections are shown in green. In this depiction, both the outlier detection component and the low-pass filtering component are observable. Further, the detected outliers are depicted with red colored "x" marks. Note that only the unfiltered detections that are not considered outliers contribute to the final filtered estimate, according to eq. (2). It is important to highlight that, when the UAV operates at a greater distance from the target, the D455 camera sensor captures a larger field of view, resulting in an increased number of false positive detections. On the contrary, as the UAV approaches the target, the target becomes bigger in the image, and the detection's precision increases. At this point, the effect of the low-pass filtering becomes more pronounced; the target detection converges to the real target,

Fig. 8: Target's pose estimation during one of the flights. The unfiltered (raw) target detections ${}_w p_t^R$, are depicted with black colored dots. The filtered ${}_w p_t[n]$, target detections are depicted with green colored "stars". The detected outliers are depicted with red colored "x" marks.

and estimates contribute to the calculation of the point of contact. This phenomenon is better illustrated in Figure 9, where between 0 and 40 [samples] the UAV operates at a larger distance, i.e., larger FOV (field of view) and the raw detection signal fluctuates with greater amplitude. The time between 40 and 67 [samples] refers to the UAV's servoing and interaction process where the target is in close proximity which corresponds to a shorter FOV where limited outlier detections are observed. Finally, for the remaining time, the UAV distanced itself from the target which resulted again in a larger FOV and larger fluctuations in the detection signal.

For the depicted experiment, the utilized parameters are selected to be $N = 20$ [samples], $d_{th} = 0.25$ [m] in 3D, and $MNDO = 40$ [samples]. N represents the averaging filtering window and controls the high-frequency rejection. Here, it was important to achieve a stable enough estimate so that the contact is considered safe and robust. The selection of N depends on the frequency of the raw detection along with its variation in a short time. In particular, the target detection algorithm operates at ~ 3 [Hz]; thus, the selected N parameters consider a relatively large history of samples (approximately 6.7 [s]) in the low-pass filtering process.

Fig. 9: Extract of the target detection and estimation during a flight over the detection samples number. The red colored signal shows the filtered detected samples ${}_w p_t[n]$, while the black colored signal, shows unfiltered (raw) detection ${}_w p_t^R$ in X, Y, Z .

Fig. 10: XYZ position of the UAV during the experiment, including the different phases of the flight.

The d_{th} parameter follows the safety consideration of the proposed design. Errors larger than the selected value could result in unsafe contact angles during the interaction phase. Finally, the $MNDO$ parameter was selected while considering the unfiltered detection rate and evaluating the occurrence of outliers. A smaller $MNDO$ value considers a shorter sample history, and thus can result in selecting different targets while the UAV operates at a larger distance from the target. All the discussed parameters were selected accordingly based on the complexity and richness of the operating environment (scene), yet it is important to highlight that limited fine-tuning was necessary to retain a stable estimate (based on the complexity of the background information).

Fig. 11: 2D trajectory of the UAV during the experiment, including the different phases of the flight and the pipe (the full grey circle). Takeoff starts in manual mode from the bottom-left, followed by servoing and then interaction mode. Manual is then used again to get away from the pipe. The dashed circle indicates the position that the UAV reaches when the manipulator gets in contact with the pipe.

B. Servoing and interaction results

The world position of the UAV is shown in Figure 10, which includes the different modes over time. As it shows, the pilot arrives to a position close to the pipe in *Manual* mode, where the target detector can estimate properly the position and orientation of the goal point. After that, the pilot switches with the RC to the *Servoing* mode, where the UAV moves to the approaching position and orientates the manipulator perpendicular to the target's surface. Then, the pilot switches to the *Interaction* mode, where the UAV finally contacts the target. While the different modes could be combined in an autonomous way based on the target's distance, we prefer to have always the pilot in the loop for safety reason. During the *Interaction* mode the UAV touches the pipe as its reference is a point that is inside the pipeline. This can be observed during $t = [30, 35]$ s in Figure 10, as the UAV keeps the same position. Finally, the pilot can decide when to finish the operation by switching to *Manual* mode and landing.

Moreover, Figure 11 presents the 2D trajectory of the UAV during the experiment and the pipe.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we demonstrated a framework for semi-autonomous detection and interaction with pipes using a UAV in a GNSS-denied environment. We could summarize our experience in the following learnings:

- Off-the-shelf solutions for GNSS-denied navigation, like T265 cameras, can provide stable odometry with some engineering: vibrations insulation and correct placement of the field of view, as direct sunlight and lack of feature can make the system diverge quickly.
- We could localize the target with the right estimation pipeline, despite false positives and drifting odometry.
- Despite the high autonomy level of the servoing and interaction controllers, the presence of the pilot was

of utmost importance to guarantee the mission's safety. Also, as the pilot is in charge of switching between different controllers, mission-specific heuristics were not necessary, improving the generality of the method.

In future developments, we aim at improving the onboard localization with a 3D lidar sensor, to avoid the downsides of visual-inertial odometry. Also we will change the target with a real fracture in the pipe, such to further validate our system in an even more realistic scenario.

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